

THE CONCEPT OF EVIDENCE IN ECONOMIC PROCEEDINGS AND ITS MEANING

Ibratova Feruza

Professor of Tashkent State Law University, Doctor of Law

Utalova Sevara

Student of Tashkent State law university

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ANNOTATION

The article discusses the use of evidence in economic proceedings, the subject of proof and the limits of proof, which are defined differently for different categories of cases. It is concluded that the evidence helps to establish the objective facts of the case and develop a reasonable conclusion in the trial of an economic dispute.

Key words: evidence, economic process, fact, exemption from evidence, means of proof, jurisprudence.

The concept of “evidence” is key both in the theory of knowledge and in the philosophy of science - as it is key in epistemology. Of course, it does not belong to the exclusive sphere of logic, philosophy or science: one constantly hears about evidence in varying depths of understanding not only - and not even primarily - from philosophers, but also from jurists (judges and lawyers), historians and scientists. Journalists and reporters conducting investigations (including the so-called “yellow press”), as well as representatives of almost all other professions, constantly resort to evidence.

They constantly use this word in everyday, everyday speech, proving to each other this or that position, point of view or personal decision. Thus, the concept of “proof” itself has stronger theoretical foundations than other key concepts that play an equally prominent role in philosophy¹.

Within any proof one can distinguish permanent structural units corresponding to its fundamental task. First of all, the message or thesis expressed directly or held in mind is highlighted - a certain statement that needs to be proven. The second point is those confirmations, grounds or arguments with the help of which the thesis is proven². For example, the thesis “copper is a conductor of electric current” can be proven using true arguments: “copper is a metal” and “all metals, by definition, are conductors of electric current.”

¹ Пирматов О. ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚ (ИҚТИСОДИЙ ВА ФУҚАРОЛИК) ДА ДАЛИЛЛАР КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯСИ //Proceedings of International Educators Conference. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 105-108.

² Babakulovna I. F., Ibratova F. B., Yerkebayeva Z. A. Mediation as an alternative way to resolution of economic disputes. – 2023.

Evidence (in jurisprudence) - information about facts obtained in the manner prescribed by law, on the basis of which the presence or absence of circumstances that are important for the correct consideration and resolution of the case is established³.

Thus, in jurisprudence, evidence is understood as information, that is, the result of cognitive activity, while in logic, evidence is the substantiation of truth, that is, an action.

Cognitive activity aimed at obtaining evidence in order to establish the truth is called proof in jurisprudence. Proof consists of collecting, securing, checking and evaluating evidence⁴.

The most important concepts in the law of evidence are the subject of proof and the limits of proof, which are defined differently for different categories of cases.

Economic procedural law is an important area of law that regulates economic relations and processes arising in the course of economic activity. There is a wealth of evidence in this area of law that plays an important role in resolving economic disputes and conflicts. In this essay we will consider the main types of evidence in economic procedural law and their importance for ensuring fairness and legality⁵.

One of the main types of evidence in economic procedural law are documents. Documents can be different: these can be contracts, invoices, accounting reports, financial documents, etc.⁶. Documents play a key role in resolving disputes in economic cases, as they provide objective data on the economic activities of the parties and can serve as the basis for a court decision.

Another important type of evidence is witness testimony. Witnesses can be participants in economic relations or persons who have information about a controversial legal fact. Their testimony can help establish the circumstances of the case and identify facts relevant to the resolution of the dispute.

Evidence in economic procedural law also includes expert opinions. Experts are specialists in a certain field of knowledge who conduct an independent

³ Закурлаев А. РАҚАМЛИ ДАЛИЛЛАРНИ АНИҚЛАШ, ҚАЙД ЭТИШ ВА ОЛИБ ЭКСПЕРТИЗА ЎТКАЗИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 151-155.

⁴ Babakulovna I. F., Ibratova F. B., Yerkebayeva Z. A. Mediation as an alternative way to resolution of economic disputes. – 2023.

⁵ Турдиев Л. З. ИШНИ СУДГА ҚАДАР ЮРИТИШДА ДАЛИЛ: ТУШУНЧАСИ ВА ТЎПЛАШ ТАРТИБИ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 96-98.

⁶ Boboqulovna I. F. et al. HAKAMLIK SUDI VA DAVLAT SUDLARI O 'RTASIDAGI FARQ QILUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 110-115.

examination at the request of the court or the parties to the case. The expert report may contain important information about the technical aspects of the case, financial calculations or other aspects that require specialized knowledge to understand⁷.

Another type of evidence is material objects. In some cases, material objects can play a key role in resolving economic disputes - for example, when it comes to the quality of goods or the performance of work.

Finally, a very important type of evidence is information from open sources - for example, data from government statistical services or other bodies. It can serve as a basis for analyzing the current state of the market or determining the cost of goods and services.

In conclusion, we can say that all of the listed types of evidence play an important role in economic jurisdiction. They help to establish the objective facts of the case and develop a reasonable conclusion of the trial in an economic dispute. Thus, these types of evidence are an integral part of ensuring justice and legality in resolving economic conflicts.

Economic procedural law is a branch of law that regulates relations related to economic activity, including the resolution of economic disputes. Evidence in economic procedural law plays a key role in establishing facts and substantiating the legal positions of the parties⁸.

The first aspect is the types of evidence in economic procedural law. In this part, you can describe types of evidence such as written documents, witness statements, expert opinions, etc. It is also worth paying attention to the peculiarities of presenting and evaluating evidence in economic disputes.

Next, we can begin to analyze the significance of evidence in economic procedural law. Here you can discuss what consequences may arise if the evidence presented is insufficient or illegal for one of the parties to the dispute. It is also worth considering the parties' obligations to provide evidence and possible sanctions for evading this responsibility.

An important topic for consideration will also be the use of electronic evidence in economic procedural law. With the development of information technology, the presentation of electronic data as evidence is becoming

⁷ Kosimov S. ДАЛИЛЛАРНИНГ КЕЛИБ ЧИҚИШИ ТАРИХИ ВА ТАСНИФИ //Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 174-181.

⁸ Feruza I., Madina A., Asal R. LEGAL ISSUES OF JUDICIAL PROTECTION IN THE ECONOMIC COURT IN UZBEKISTAN //International journal of professional science. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 5-10.

increasingly important. But at the same time, new problems arise related to confirming the authenticity of electronic data and maintaining their integrity⁹.

You can also touch upon the topic of using international evidence in economic disputes. With the globalization of the economy, situations increasingly arise where the use of documentation or testimony from other countries is necessary to resolve disputes.

Finally, the prospects for the development of requirements for the presentation and evaluation of evidence in economic procedural law should also be discussed. Technological advances and changing business practices require constant review and modification of requirements for the presentation and evaluation of evidence.

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⁹ Хабибуллаев Д. Некоторые вопросы совершенствования гражданского процессуального кодекса Республики Узбекистан //Review of law sciences. – 2017. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 75-79.

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